

Frameworks and Strategies to Improve Inclusion of Underserved Groups in Myeloma Clinical Trials (EQUAL-ME Project): A Scoping Review Protocol

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Abstract

Objective: To map out the breadth of evidence on existing frameworks, toolkits, initiatives and best practice guides intended to support the recruitment of under-served populations into clinical trials and identify knowledge and practice gaps.

Introduction: Without greater representation in clinical trials, disparities in cancer burden for underserved groups may increase. Better inclusion of real-world populations fosters more equitable, effective, and trusted advances in treatment for all myeloma patients. There is no consensus on how to improve the inclusion of under-served populations in European myeloma clinical trials.

Inclusion criteria: Trial participants from underserved or under-represented groups in clinical research (population); any framework, actionable steps, checklists, toolkit, guideline, best practice, practical recommendations or method explicitly intended to support inclusion of underserved or under-represented groups (concept); human clinical trials of any phase, in any disease area,

worldwide (context). Literature limited solely to highlighting existing inequity or to broad conceptual discussions, and languages other than English, Spanish and Portuguese, will be excluded.

Methods: A search for relevant literature will be conducted in 4 databases: Medline (Ovid), Embase (Ovid), PsycINFO, and ERIC. Grey literature will be searched using Google search engine. We will also search the websites of 'key partners' (e.g., EU ethics bodies, sponsors) and use reference chaining to identify other sources. No language filters will be applied to the search at this point, as it may risk removing relevant results, or introduce bias. Screening, selection, and data extraction will be performed by 2 independent reviewers until acceptable IRR score is achieved for each screening stage.

Keywords: Clinical trials; Inclusion; Trial design; Myeloma; Underserved populations.

Introduction

Drug development depends on robust clinical trials, with participant populations that represent real-world populations and results that are generalisable. Considering the equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) aspects of trials is critical to ensuring that results are generalisable and to improve representation from groups that have been historically underrepresented in research.

“Underserved” populations may be defined but not limited to characteristics such as¹:

- Lower inclusion in research than one would expect from population estimates
- High healthcare burden that is not matched by the volume of research designed for the group
- Important differences in how a group responds to or engages with healthcare interventions compared to other groups, with research neglecting to address these factors

Underrepresentation can be driven by demographics (age, sex, ethnicity, education), socioeconomic factors (employment, rurality, language, digital access, religion), health status (mental illness, addiction, disability, obesity) and disease-specific features (rare or genetic sub-types).

Understanding and addressing these disparities is crucial for ensuring equitable access to clinical trials and cutting-edge treatments, and for improving outcomes for all myeloma patients. However, these characteristics rarely sit in isolation. Intersectionality is the principle that social identities (e.g., gender, race, sexuality and class) are intertwined and co-constitutive, challenging unitary identity categories and revealing how overlapping identities create distinct experiences.^{2,3}

Ethnicity and race are two of many dimensions of underserved populations in clinical trials. Although nuanced and often used interchangeably, ethnicity refers to shared cultural characteristics such as language, ancestry, practices and beliefs⁴ while race is typically used to classify people based on perceived physical traits such as skin colour⁴. Although often used interchangeably, the two describe different aspects of identity. Moreover, race is now widely recognised as a social and political construct rather than a valid biological construct⁵, but still relevant for the racial identity and organisation of different ethnic minorities. And although race/ethnicity is not “biology”, it can still be biologically informative in clinical trials. For instance, in other disease areas, evidence suggests that differences in genetic ancestry may introduce genetic variation with the potential to

alter therapeutic efficacy⁶, and that race and ethnicity, although being non-reliable indicators for genetic diversity, it may be associated with differences in how people respond to medicines (e.g., adverse reactions)⁷. In myeloma, evidence of racial differences in cytogenetic abnormalities⁸, together with ongoing discussions regarding the multifactorial and complex nature of racial disparities in myeloma, reinforce the need for trial generalisability that encompasses both the 'social' and 'biological' dimensions. Ultimately, there is strong evidence to suggest that increased inclusion of underserved groups in clinical trials is one of the most important factors⁹ in eliminating disparities in survival and advancing cancer care for all.

The majority of evidence on ethnic minority inclusion in clinical research is from the United States (US), with relatively little other research globally^{10,11}. The majority of studies focusing on ethnic minority inclusion in clinical trials have been found to be from US perspectives, focusing more on US populations, with fewer studies evaluating representation of racial groups from different countries.¹²

In the US the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has launched programs and initiatives designed to enhance diversity in oncology clinical trials.^{13,14} FDA's legislative mandate for Diversity Action Plans (2022) and draft guidance published in 2024¹⁵, encourages sponsors to submit diversity action plans early in the drug development process, outlining enrolment goals and strategies to include underrepresented populations. It has been positively recognised by the American Society of Hematology (ASH) as a constructive step toward improving representation in clinical trials, as it may encourage sponsors to incorporate diverse participation and create accountability for diverse trial recruitment.¹⁶

There are some examples of diversity initiatives demonstrating measurable gains. For example, Pfizer's internal analysis of 213 U.S. clinical trials conducted between 2011 and 2020 found that Black or African American participation (14.3%) matched their share of the U.S. population (13.4%), and over 56% of trials achieved census-level inclusion for this group.¹⁷ Another example comes from a recent AstraZeneca report¹⁸ highlighting its success in enrolling diverse groups in clinical trials, with representation broadly aligned to U.S. Census data. The report describes AstraZeneca's efforts to enhance diversity and shows that the company adopted (along with other US federal policies and legislation) measures informed by FDA guidance and recommendations over the years, demonstrating the influence of such regulatory standards on trial inclusion outcomes.

Evidence from the US shows that legislation, formal guidance, and accountability mechanisms can drive measurable improvements in inclusion¹⁹. However, policy shifts²⁰, along with the differences in health systems^{21,22} and demographics exposes a clear need for a tailored approach in Europe. Directly replicating US measures would be inappropriate.²³ European clinical trials require bespoke strategies where lessons from US successes can be adapted, not simply replicated.

Without greater inclusion in European trials, disparities in cancer burden among underserved groups are likely to widen. In myeloma, people of African descent, are a widely documented underserved group, especially in US literature^{9,24,25}. Evidence suggests that observed disparities do not arise from a single factor but reflect a range of potential mechanisms, both biological and non-biological.⁹ These include differences in disease biology and response to treatment, variation in exposure to risk factors associated with cancer development, and inequities in access to timely diagnosis and high-quality care. Greater inclusion of underserved populations in research studies, including clinical trials, is therefore essential to better understand and address these disparities for all cancer

patients. This is also relevant in Europe, where African, Afro-Caribbean, and other migrant communities are part of the patient population.

Overall, racial and ethnic minorities, older adults, and socioeconomically disadvantaged groups have worse outcomes in myeloma.²⁶ In the European context, inequalities may be influenced by differences in language, healthcare systems, access to specialist care, and the challenges associated with rurality. For example, in Central and Eastern Europe and the Baltics, slower adoption of innovative therapies and gaps in early diagnosis contribute to poorer outcomes compared with Western Europe.²⁷ These and other structural barriers highlight the importance of increasing representation in European myeloma clinical trials and developing context-specific strategies to close the gaps between different patient populations.

This project aims to map the breadth of evidence on efforts to improve the inclusion of underserved groups in clinical trials. Given the diversity of study designs and conceptual approaches within this field, a scoping review will enable a comprehensive overview of existing research, identification of knowledge gaps, and exploration of key concepts. A preliminary search of PROSPERO, an international systematic review registry, was conducted and no current or underway systematic reviews or scoping reviews on the topic were identified. However, we have identified an existing scoping review, covering a broader topic, published by Mishra et al.²⁸ The review by Mishra et al was designed to capture all mentions of equity, diversity and inclusion in clinical trials, from conceptual discussions to data analyses. Our focus is on improvement efforts only i.e., frameworks for inclusion of underserved groups in clinical trials. Consequently, our scoping review search will be expanded, by adding the concepts of 'Framework' 'Trial participation' and with key words such as 'toolkit', 'checklist', 'recruitment', 'enrol*', respectively. Our review also expands the date of publication from 2023-2025 to capture recent advances in the field. While elements of the search were informed by Mishra et al, the present scoping review adopts a distinct focus, scope, and conceptual framework, expanding substantially beyond the parameters of that earlier work. We will include relevant papers identified by Mishra et al. along with updating the literature search for any additional, more recently published frameworks.

This scoping review is the first phase of a multi-stage research project²⁹ to identify barriers, build consensus, and create solutions and recommendations for the inclusion of underserved populations in European myeloma clinical trials. Myeloma is a cancer of the plasma cells found in the bone marrow.³⁰ Although it accounts for only 1% of all cancers, it is the third most common haematological malignancy in Europe³¹ with a growing disease burden in an aging population.³² The disease is incurable and prone to relapse and drug resistance, however, advancements in myeloma treatment have led to substantial improvements in progression-free survival and overall survival. Disparities in access to care and clinical trial participation persist across different populations within Europe^{33,34}, significantly impacting the quality of care received by patients and contributing to poorer outcomes.

The objective of this scoping review is to identify and appraise what frameworks, toolkits, guidelines, initiatives, best practices, recommendations or methods (concept) that have been developed to improve the inclusion of underserved trials participants (population) in clinical trials (context).

Review question

What frameworks, toolkits, guidelines, initiatives, best practices, recommendations, or methods have been developed to improve the inclusion of underserved or under-represented participants in clinical trials?

Inclusion criteria

Participants

Trial participants from underserved or under-represented groups in clinical research. “Underserved” defined as those with lower-than-expected inclusion in research, a disproportionately high healthcare burden unmet by existing studies, or distinct responses to interventions that have been largely overlooked.¹

Concept

Any tool, framework, set of actionable steps, checklist, toolkit, guideline, best practice, practical recommendation, or method—hereafter collectively referred to as *Frameworks*—defined as a structured, evidence-informed model designed to guide actions, interventions, or policies addressing a specific issue, explicitly intended to enhance the inclusion of underserved or under-represented groups.

Context

Human clinical trials of any phase, in any disease area, worldwide.

Types of sources

This scoping review will consider both experimental and quasi-experimental study designs including randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials, before and after studies and interrupted time-series studies. In addition, analytical observational studies including prospective and retrospective cohort studies, case-control studies and analytical cross-sectional studies will be considered for inclusion. This review will also consider descriptive observational study designs including case series, individual case reports and descriptive cross-sectional studies for inclusion.

Qualitative studies will also be considered that focus on qualitative data including, but not limited to, designs such as phenomenology, grounded theory, ethnography, qualitative description, action research and feminist research.

In addition, systematic reviews that meet the inclusion criteria will also be considered, depending on the research question and the recommendations included.

Text and opinion papers will also be considered for inclusion in this scoping review.

Methods

The proposed scoping review will be conducted in accordance with the JBI methodology for scoping reviews³⁵. This protocol will be published in a registry (Zenodo) for transparency and avoiding duplication: DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17602139

Search strategy

The search strategy will aim to locate both published and unpublished studies. A three-step search strategy will be utilized in this review:

Before developing the formal search strategy, an exploratory examination of the literature was conducted to identify relevant reviews and examples of search strategies in this field. During this process, a peer-reviewed paper by Mishra et al.²⁸ was identified. The approach described by Mishra et al. informed the initial development of the search strategy for the present review.

Step 1 – Initial limited search:

An initial limited search of key databases (MEDLINE and Embase) was undertaken to identify articles on the topic. Concepts and terminology identified during this step, along with those reported by Mishra *et al.*, informed the refinement of the initial search strategy.

Step 2 – Comprehensive search:

The adapted search strategy incorporated additional concepts such as *framework* and *trial participation*, as well as related keywords (e.g., *toolkit*, *checklist*, *recruitment*, *enrol*). The final strategy was developed iteratively through team discussion and was designed to comprehensively capture operationalisation approaches related to inclusion in clinical trials. The search will be conducted across MEDLINE (Ovid), Embase (Ovid), ERIC, and PsycINFO, with the strategy adapted for each database and information source. The complete adapted search strategy is presented in Appendix I.

Studies published in English, Portuguese, and Spanish will be included, as these are the languages spoken by the reviewers.

Step 3 – Citation search and grey literature:

To ensure completeness, the reference lists of included studies in this scoping review will be screened for additional sources. Grey literature will be searched using Google, combining relevant keywords (e.g., inclusion, underserved, framework, clinical trials) and screening the first 100 results. Websites of key partners and organisations (e.g., EU ethics bodies, sponsors) will also be searched

for potentially relevant unpublished materials. Additional literature may be added with input from the project's steering group upon relevance.

Study/Source of evidence selection

Following the search, all identified citations will be exported in RIS format and uploaded into Covidence© 2025 (Veritas Health Innovation Ltd, Melbourne, VI) and duplicates removed. Based on Cochrane guidance³⁶, title and abstract screening process will consist of two reviewers independently screening 10% of records and assessing reviewer agreement. This process will be repeated by reviewers until the desirable agreement rate is reached. If the score is good ($\geq 80\%$), the remainder of records will be screened by a single reviewer.

Potentially relevant sources will be retrieved in full and screened using Covidence©. The full text of selected citations will be assessed in detail against the inclusion criteria by two or more independent reviewers. Reasons for exclusion of sources of evidence at full text that do not meet the inclusion criteria will be recorded and reported in the scoping review. 10% of citations will be double-screened until reviewers reach the acceptable agreement score ($\geq 80\%$). Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers at each stage of the selection process will be resolved through discussion, or with an additional reviewer/s. The results of the search and the study inclusion process will be reported in full in the final scoping review and presented in a PRISMA flow diagram. The results of the search and the study inclusion process will be reported in full in the final scoping review and presented in a PRISMA flow diagram³⁷.

A draft PRISMA flow diagram is attached in the appendices to illustrate the data collection process, including grey literature (Appendix III).

Data extraction

Data will be extracted from papers included in the scoping review by two or more independent reviewers using a data extraction tool developed by the reviewers. The data extraction tool will be developed by authors based on initial charting table from Excel with columns containing relevant elements (e.g. title, publication year, study type, framework of EDI, summary/purpose, research stage). The data extracted will include specific details about the participants, concept, context, study methods and key findings relevant to the review question/s.

A draft extraction form is provided (see Appendix II). The draft data extraction tool will be modified and revised as necessary during the process of extracting data from each included evidence source. Modifications will be detailed in the scoping review. Piloting of the data extraction form will be conducted on 10% of records to ensure that all team members perform it consistently and correctly. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers will be resolved through discussion, or with an additional reviewer/s. If appropriate, authors of papers will be contacted to request missing or additional data, where required.

Data analysis and presentation

The scoping review will consist of a descriptive synthesis and gap analysis. The results will be presented in graphic and tabular format, accompanied by a narrative summary.

Funding

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Declarations

The authors are committed to promoting equity, diversity, and inclusion in research. This project, which focuses on the inclusion of underserved groups in myeloma clinical trials, was guided by a diverse Steering Committee to ensure a range of perspectives were represented. The research team is diverse and brings previous experience in equality-focused research, which has informed the development of this protocol and overall project.

Author contributions

In accordance with the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors recommendations (ICMJE Recommendations 2018) authorship will be based on four criteria;

- I. substantial contributions to the conception or design of the work, or the acquisition, analysis, or interpretation of data for the work; AND
- II. drafting the work or revising it critically for important intellectual content. AND
- III. final approval of the version to be published; AND
- IV. agreement to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved.

All individuals meeting all four criteria will be identified as authors. Any individuals who meet some, but do not meet all, criteria will be named within the acknowledgements provided they consent to this.

Conflicts of interest

Authors report the following relationships, all of which are unrelated to the scoping review:

RP had research support and roles as Principal Investigator for studies funded by GSK and Pfizer; consultancy for GSK, Roche and Johnson & Johnson (J&J); honoraria from Johnson & Johnson (J&J), AbbVie, GSK, Bristol Myers Squibb (BMS) and Pfizer; membership on Scientific Advisory Boards for Johnson & Johnson (J&J), Roche and GSK; and travel or meeting attendance support from Johnson & Johnson (J&J) and GSK.

CC had consultancy, advisory or speaker roles for AbbVie, Binding Site, Genentech, GSK, Johnson & Johnson (J&J), Pfizer, Sanofi, Regeneron and Bristol Myers Squibb (BMS); and involvement as a researcher on studies funded by AbbVie and GSK.

SD is part of the Advisory Group for Representation in Global Clinical Trials for Boehringer Ingelheim (BI).

ED, JS and MR are employed at Myeloma Patients Europe, a non-profit umbrella organisation of local and national patient support organisations across Europe. Myeloma Patients Europe work is supported by grants from pharmaceutical companies and from public sources. Full disclosure of organizations financing can be found at <https://www.mpeurope.org/about-mpe/our-funding/>.

The remaining authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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Appendices

Appendix I: Search strategy

MEDLINE (Ovid) - Search conducted on 07/2025

EDI (Equity, Diversity, Inclusion)	Trial Participation	Frameworks/tools/etc	Clinical trials	Filters
(includi* or Equit* or diversity or disadvantaged or representation or exclusion or inclusion or underprivileged or underserved or underrepresented or "underserved communities" or minorit* or minority group* or disparit* or "racial disparity*" or race-based disparities or "health disparit*" or "health inequit*" or "health in equalit*" or "gaps" or "disproportionate burden" or "socially disadvantaged" or "vulnerable population*" or "historically disadvantaged" or "historically underrepresented" or "inclusive representation" or "low socioeconomic status" or "marginalised group*" or "marginalised population*")OR ("underserved" OR "underserved" OR "underrepresented" OR "underrepresented" OR "seldom heard" OR "seldom heard" OR "hard to reach" OR "hard-to reach" OR "minority" OR "minorities" OR "marginalised" OR "marginalized" OR "discriminated" OR "deprived")	(Enrol* or Recruit* or Participat* or Trial participant) OR ((enrol* or recruit*) adj5 (method* or strateg* or approach?? or intervention? or "best practice?" or diversity or underserve* or underrepresent* or minorit*)). OR ((recruit* or enrol* or participat* or enter* or entry or engag* or accrue*) adj5 (trial? or study or research))	(Framework OR checklist or Guidelines or Guidance or Recommendation or Best practice or Roadmap or Improvement or Intervention or Interventions or Tool* or Resource or Resources or Strategy or strategies or Blueprint or Approaches or Approach or operationalisation or operationalization or standard)	"Clinical Trials as Topic"[Mesh]	Humans/Human subjects 2023 - current date

General information:

Study ID (text field)

Title (text field)

Title of paper / abstract / report that data are extracted from

Year of publication (text field)

Country in which the study was conducted (check boxes - multiple)

Based on country of data collection (if reported). If not reported, use first or corresponding author's affiliation.

1. United States
2. United Kingdom
3. Australia
4. Canada
5. Other Europe: specify
6. Other: specify

What is the primary source of sponsorship or institutional affiliation of the study? (check box - single)

1. Industry
2. Academic/Public funds
3. Mixed
4. Not reported

Link (text field)

DOI, journal page, pdf link, webpage

Framework (tool/ guideline/ best practice) information:

Framework name (text field)

Name of Framework/ tool/ guideline/ best practice (if applicable)

Purpose/aim of framework (text field)

Intended Underserved Population (check boxes- multiple)

Underserved group(s) framework/tool is intended for (including PRO-EDI tool characteristics¹)

1. Race (physical/biological characteristics)/Ethnicity (broader than race, cultural identification)
2. Sex (i.e. male/female/intersex)
3. Gender (i.e. woman/man/non-binary/trans, boys/girls)

4. Sexual identity
5. Disability
6. Age
7. Socio-Economic Status (i.e. occupation/employment/income)
8. Level of Education
9. Health literacy
10. Geographical (i.e. country of study, rural/urban)
11. Language/cultural
12. Immigrant/refugee
13. Mental health
14. Comorbidities (e.g., obesity)
15. Impaired capacity for consent
16. Other: specify
17. Unclear

Please specify subgroup (if applicable) (text box)

If the framework/tool focuses on a specific subgroup within the identified underserved population(s), please specify the subgroup(s) in the text box below

Intended audience/user (check boxes)

Audience/user tool is intended for (e.g., trial sponsor/trial recruiter)

1. Sponsors/funders
2. Trial teams/recruiters
3. Ethical bodies
4. Regulatory/Payer bodies
5. Other: specify
6. Unclear

Intended trial type (text field) (e.g. Type/phase of trial tool is intended for registrational trials, academic trials, or not specified)

Summary of recommendations (text field)

Intended application in the research lifecycle point (checkboxes)

Select all applicable lifecycle points for which the framework is aimed

1. Planning/ Design
2. Recruitment
3. Ongoing trial conduct
4. Reporting/ Dissemination/ Assessment
5. Other: specify
6. Unclear

Intended geographical coverage (check boxes- single)

1. Single country
2. Multi-country
3. Global
4. Unclear/Not specified

Please specify the country/countries included in the geographical coverage (text field)

European country included in intended application

1. Yes
2. No
3. Unclear

Further resources to be release (check box - single)

1. Yes
2. No
3. Not applicable

If applicable, include the anticipated date of resources being available

Notes (text field)

Items from AGREE II² deemed relevant and adapted for use in this review:

Stakeholder involvement

- 1. The views and preferences of the target population (i.e. the underserved group(s)) have been sought**

Rigour of development

- 2. The framework/tool/ guideline/ best practice is based on evidence**

Transferability (items from CEBM Critical Appraisal of qualitative studies⁴)

- 3. Are the findings transferable to other clinical settings?**

1. Yes - intended in the design
2. Yes- can be reasonably assumed
3. No - specified non-transferable

4. No - does not appear to be
5. Unclear/Not Applicable

4. Are the findings transferable to other geographical settings?

1. Yes - intended in the design
 2. Yes- can be reasonably assumed
 3. No - specified non-transferable
 4. No - does not appear to be
 5. Unclear/Not Applicable
-

References

1. PRO-EDI tool: [PRO EDI: improving how equity, diversity and inclusion are handled in evidence synthesis • Trial Forge](#)
2. AGREE II: [Microsoft Word - AGREE II - User's Manual and 23-item Instrument FINAL VERSION 2009 UPDATE 2013.docx](#)
3. EMERGE tool: [‘EMERGE’: Construction of a simple quality appraisal tool for rapid review of laparoscopic surgery guidelines during COVID-19 pandemic - PMC](#)
4. CEBM Critical Appraisal of Qualitative Studies: [Qualitative-Studies.pdf](#)

Appendix III: PRISMA flow diagram (draft)

